

Leaf chlorosis due to infestation by a new cyst nematode

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Cyst nematodes of the genus *Heterodera* have reportedly attacked upland rice in Japan and lowland rice in the Ivory Coast. The parasite causes browning, reduction of root hairs, and retardation of physiological functioning of roots. The chief foliar symptoms are retarded plant growth, depleted vigor, and leaf chlorosis.

Recent surveys for parasitic nematodes of rice and rice soils in the Indian northeastern states, Orissa and Kerala showed *H. oryzae* prevalent in Orissa, and Assam. In the upland rice areas on the Rice Research Farms at Pattambi and Mannuty in Kerala, standing rice crops at 50-70 days of age suffered from leaf chlorosis. Examination of roots showed the presence of cyst nematode, blackening of roots, and loss of root hairs. The nematode cysts resembled *H. elachista* in shape but differed in the structure of vulval cone. Each contained an egg sac attached to its vulva (see figure). Because the second-stage juveniles differed in dimension from those of *H. oryzae*, the cyst nematode may be considered a new species.

Greenhouse tests in which rice varieties IR8 and the cultivar CRM 13-3241 (an irradiated culture of the cross NSJ 200/Padma) were inoculated with infective juveniles of the new cyst nematode confirmed the pathogenicity of the nematode. Typical symptoms of leaf chlorosis and root browning occurred 15 days after infestation of the root by the nematode. Analysis of chlorophyll in leaves of healthy and infected plants of CRM 13-3241 at 15, 25, and 35 days after inoculation showed reduction by 20.9%, 58.6%, and 74.2%, respectively. Affected plants flowered 10 days earlier and had reduced grain weight. The nematode completed its life cycle from

Cyst of Heterodera sp in situ on root of IR8.

27 to 32 days after inoculation and the eggs from egg sac or cyst readily hatched in water. Further work on the identification of the new nematode, evaluation of damage and yield losses, and development of control measures is in progress. ❧

Effect of Hinosan and foliar micronutrient sprays on brown-spot disease of rice

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The effectiveness of two foliar micronutrient sprays and of Hinosan (O-ethyl S, S. diphenyl phosphorodithioate) against brown spot of rice caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan was tested in a field trial during *samba* season (Sept. 1976 – Jan. 1977).

A 1% solution of “733,” 1% and 1.5% solutions of “755,” and 0.08% solution of Hinosan were used. “F33” contained (by weight) Cu, 10%; MG(OH)₂, NH₃, KBr, S, Ca, and

catalysts 30%; Zn, 2.5%; Mn, 2.5%; Bo 2.5%; and traces of Mb, Vn, Co, and Ni. “F55” is like “F33,” except that its Cu content is 20%. The solutions were sprayed 65, 85, and 105 days after seeding. All treatments reduced disease incidence. Hinosan and “F55” at 1.5% reduced leaf and grain infections. Increased grain yield was recorded for Hinosan- and “F55”-treated plots. ❧

Isolation of the brown leaf spot pathogen of rice from soil

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In an experiment to standardize the isolation from soil of the brown leaf spot pathogen of rice *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, the pathogen was isolated in Czapek-Dox-Agar and rice agar media. The systemic fungicide Benlate was incorporated in the media at 100, 250, and 500 ppm. The pathogen was recovered from both media, but more from the rice agar medium (see table). ❧

Isolation of *H. oryzae* from soil, Tamil Nadu, India.

Medium	Benlate(ppm)		
	100	250	500
Czapek-Dox-Agar	1.41 ^a	1.92	2.48
Rice agar	2.14	2.13	3.34

^aColonies (x 10³)/g of soil (wet wt).

Seasonal variation of rice reactions to blast in Taiwan

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Blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is one major disease of rice in Taiwan. Until recently, it was more commonly observed during the cool first-crop season and it tended to cause more damage on ponlai

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